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The interleukin IL-32 is activated during senescence.

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Cellular senescence was characterized by induction of the cytokine interleukin IL-32.

1 **Results**

2 We measured total transcription in young and senescent human umbilical vein endothelial
3 (HUVEC) cells to understand, study and comprehensively define the senescence program in *Homo*
4 *sapiens*. We discovered activation of IL-32 as an essential component of senescence in human cells
(**Figure 1**).

5 **Figure 1: Activation of IL-32 is an essential component of the senescence program.**

6 GSE155680

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GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
9235	6.57E-154	0.0651	-26.427776	-1.719461	3558.08	IL32	128/15580	99.2

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9 We observed strong activation of IL-32 in senescent HUVEC (**Figure 1**).

10 We studied a second cellular model of senescence wherein we measured total transcription in
11 fibroblasts isolated from children and elderly humans to define the human senescence program in an
unbiased fashion (**Figure 2**).

12 **Figure 2: Activation of IL-32 is an essential component of the senescence program.**

13 GSE262932

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GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
9235	2.36E-40	0.339	-13.2985077	-4.5060752	279.21	IL32	164/17001	99.0

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16 In this second model, activation of IL-32 was again a defining element of the senescence gene
17 signature.

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19 **Discussion**

20 We described here the discovery of IL-32 activation as an essential component of the senescence
21 program in humans.

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